

humantech

D1.1 – The HumanTech vision and research requirements

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Abstract

The HumanTech project comprises research on different technologies to obtain a digital twin of the construction site or existing buildings, and the application of wearable devices and advanced robots in construction. All HumanTech partners envision that the application of all these technologies will lead to an advance of construction towards a safer and greener construction industry. This document will describe this unified HumanTech vision. As the main challenges for the construction industry were identified: a growing demand in construction induced by a growing demand for energy efficient renovations, infrastructure investments and urbanisation, climate change, resource scarcity and a shortage of labour. The main research requirements are extending open BIM standards for data exchange and interoperability, methods to obtain Dynamic Semantic Digital Twins of construction sites and other assets, unobtrusive wearables with intelligent transparency, robotic interfaces and learning from demonstration, on-site safe human-robot-collaboration and workflow capturing with XR visualization. The impact of HumanTech is expected in the fields of worker's health and safety and a transition towards green, climate-friendly, and resource-efficient construction by reducing errors, increasing accuracy and efficient robotic task automation.

Keywords

Open BIM, IFC, Digital twin, exoskeletons, XR-glasses, sensors, UAV, UGV, robots, human-robot collaboration, semantic modelling, health and safety, machine learning, computer vision, digitalization in construction

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
6DoF	Six degrees of freedom
AGV	Automatic guided vehicle
AR	Augmented reality
BIM	Building information modeling
BIMxD	BIM extended digital twin
bSDD	Building smart data dictionary
CO2	Carbon dioxide equivalents
DSDT	Dynamic semantic digital twin
EEG	Electroencephalogram
EU	European Union
FSR	Force sensitive resistors
GHG	Greenhouse gas
IFC	Industry foundation classes
IDM	Information delivery manual
IMU	Inertial measurement unit

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LDA	Linear discriminant analysis
SME	Small and medium enterprise
SVM	Support vector machine
ToF	Time of flight
UAV	Unmanned aerial vehicle
UGV	Unmanned ground vehicle
US	United states of America
VR	Virtual reality
XR	Extended Reality

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1. The HumanTech vision

The **European construction industry** faces three major challenges: increase the safety and wellbeing of its workforce, improve its efficiency and productivity, and become greener, making sustainable use of resources.

To address these challenges, HumanTech proposes to develop **human-centred cutting-edge technologies** such as wearables for workers' safety and support and robots that can harmoniously coexist with human workers while contributing to the ecological transition of the sector.

HumanTech aims to achieve major advances in cutting-edge technologies that will enable a safe, rewarding, and digital work environment for a new generation of highly skilled construction workers and engineers.

These advances will include:

An entirely new breed of **Dynamic Semantic Digital Twins (DSDTs)** that simulate in detail the current state of a construction site at the geometric and semantic level, based on an extended Building Information Modeling (BIM) formulation that contains all relevant structural and semantic dimensions (BIMxD). BIMxDs will act as a common reference for all human workers, engineers, and autonomous machines.

Smart, unobtrusive workers protection and support equipment. From exoskeletons activated by body sensors for posture and strain to wearable cameras and XR glasses that provide real-time workers' location and guidance to perform their tasks efficiently and accurately.

Robotic devices equipped with vision and intelligence that allow robots to navigate autonomously and safely in highly unstructured environments, collaborate with humans and dynamically update a semantic digital twin of the construction site they operate in.

By these advances safety, efficiency and sustainability will be pushed making construction industry a technology-based sector attractive to people of all sex, gender, and abilities.

DSDTs will serve as the single source of truth i.e., the consolidated source of information for the entire construction lifecycle and will have major positive effects on efficiency in construction as well as sustainability. Efficiency will be leveraged as DSDTs are the basis for machine and robotic operation by providing data

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and information about the building and its components to be produced. This information can be used to plan robotic tasks, operate machines, etc. As such, DSDTs are the premise for implementing such technologies in construction. For such applications DSDTs need regular updates to provide up-to-date information. Depending on the use case, updates need to be real-time or daily. Construction works are very prone to errors of all sorts, beginning from the planning stage with unsolved details up to on-site errors ultimately resulting in labour-intensive and difficult error fixing or even reconstruction of wrongly erected or installed components. DSDTs will overcome this as they provide up to date information. More importantly, by being updated regularly thus enabling early detection of mistakes providing time to work out solutions.

To achieve the European new Green Deal objectives and achieve the decarbonisation of the EU building stock by 2050, all players in construction need to deal responsibly with existing structures with a special focus on avoiding demolition by prioritising renovation and facilitating further use of the structure and/or its components and high-level recycling. Any structure not demolished will minimise greenhouse gas emission and usage of natural resources. The first step in the process of assessing existing structures and determining the potential for elongating their lifetime is to consolidate information about the structure. Automatic data acquisition and derived DSDTs provide such consolidated information. In HumanTech use cases, such as bridge inspection and monitoring, will be facilitated through DSDTs acquired using acquisition systems such as UAVs and UGVs. This will ultimately facilitate a safe elongation of the lifetime based on high-quality up to date information.

Wearables will help to keep workers safe by displaying dedicated information and warnings through XR glasses according to the situation the worker is in. Besides, exoskeletons activated on demand will help to support fatiguing tasks such as heavy lifting or overhead work that would also have bad consequences on the physical constitution of the worker if carried out frequently.

Human-Robot interaction is considered as a key to spread the use of robots on construction site for multiple reasons. Firstly, it seems unlikely that all tasks on site will be taken over by robots having all human staff completely off the site and thus out of potentially dangerous situations. Hence, humans and robots are expected to coexist on site for the next decades with robots that would act as additional

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smart tools. Such coexistence will only increase efficiency when workers and robots are aware of the respective next tasks, actions and even movements to ensure a safety. Secondly, construction sites are a volatile environment with almost instant changes of conditions, objects, and actors around. Thus, robots need to be adaptive and learn to deal with constantly changing environments. This will be achieved by adaptive learning but must be supported by human guidance to allow for an efficient application of robots on site.

In the following sections the approaches to DSDT generation and update, Wearables and Human-Robot interaction will be introduced.

1.1. Dynamic Semantic Digital Twin

Dynamic Semantic Digital Twin

Generating an accurate digital twin of the as-built state in a construction site is the cornerstone of any attempt to digitalize the site and use autonomous robots in collaboration with humans and other machines. The constructed digital twin will depict the site accurately in terms of geometry (3D reconstruction) as well as semantic information (object-level labels and materials information). It will form the reference framework for any robotic autonomous solution or XR visualization. It will be constructed by 3D scanning of the environment with autonomous ground and aerial vehicles (UGV, UAV) as well as processing of the acquired point clouds with machine learning AI algorithms for semantic segmentation and object recognition and alignment. The effort will also be supported by novel hardware solutions such as a spherical 360-degree RGB-D camera provided by RICOH. Continuous dynamic update of the digital twin model will be in focus, serving task planning for continuous and safe operation based on recent data. A novel BIM extended Digital Twin (BIMxD) standardization formulation with extended information on human-robotic collaborative tasks planning and scheduling as well as worker H&S and task guidance/training related information will be developed with full interoperability with existing BIM-based systems.

Green transition – Improved resource use, less errors during construction due to continuous progress monitoring

Safety and Health – Automatic identification of hazards on site

Efficiency – Improved resource and time planning, efficient progress monitoring

1.2. Wearables for efficiency and safety

Wearables for efficiency and safety

A core objective of the project is to equip the future generation of construction workers with lightweight, easy to carry and use, wearable solutions that will monitor their health-related parameters, prevent injuries and support heavy tasks while providing information that will increase decision-making accuracy and improve the training process. The integrated wearable solution will include:

- A body pose inertial sensor network, loosely and thus unobtrusively integrated in workers clothing to track body posture and guide/activate exoskeleton components.
- A miniature camera integrated in the clothing, used for vision-based precise 6DoF localization enabling XR visualizations for task assistance and providing contextual information to the inertial sensors and exoskeleton.
- An exoskeleton that will make use of the body sensing information to provide support to the worker in strenuous or repetitive tasks to reduce the impact on their health following the concept of intelligent transparency.
- XR-glasses that can be used when required for visualization of BIM information localized and overlaid over the current building state for guidance to the worker and error avoidance.

Reducing errors by displaying BIMxD information on XR glasses.

Safety and Health – Monitor worker body pose, identify stressful actions and activate support

Efficiency – BIM referencing for direct feedback/control of work, increase attractiveness of work, avoid overuse of resources

1.3. Human-Robot interaction

Human-Robot Interaction

Autonomous robots that can easily navigate through the construction site will be used as support to human workers, for example in bringing or disposing material. Within HumanTech, our aim is to develop a new generation of autonomous mobile robotic platforms for the construction industry that can work alongside human workers and take over the mundane tasks such as material transport autonomously, involving specifically:

- o A versatile autonomous ground robot, with appropriate sensory systems to safely navigate in dynamic environments.
- o A robotic solution with high-payload capacity
- o Human-machine interface for effective communication and identification of construction and demolition waste.

The goal would be to support workers in the construction industry by taking over strenuous work and preventing musculoskeletal diseases body from non-ergonomic poses (e.g., working on the floor or over-head). Executing high-risk and unhealthy tasks such as demolition in a remote-controlled semi-autonomous manner has clear benefits for the workers well-being.

	<p>Green transition – Identification of hazardous material through robotic sensing, more efficient and more accurate task execution</p>
	<p>Safety and Health – Robotic support for straining repetitive tasks, remote executions of tasks in hazardous environments</p>
	<p>Efficiency - Automation and robots are vital to bridging the digital gap in the construction industry</p>

1.4. The unified HumanTech Vision

HumanTech aims to bring AI technologies to the construction industry. For the communication of diverse intelligent components (robotics, wearables, etc.) a common reference representation system is required. This is the role of BIMxD, an extension of the BIM beyond structural models, to more detailed information on current state of building, machinery and equipment, materials as well as human resources.

The prerequisite for the utilisation of the BIMxD modelling infrastructure is the ability to maintain full up-to-date information of the construction site. This is the role of the dynamic semantic digital twin technologies developed in HumanTech. Autonomous ground and air scanning devices as well as hand-held scanners should be able to update the construction site model constantly through a process of applying semantic segmentation to 3D point clouds, and subsequent transformation/alignment with BIMxD models. To reduce the investment needed to access BIMxD technologies especially for SMEs, HumanTech partners envision open-source BIMxD authoring and interaction tools that can be used free of charge. Such tools should be accompanied by appropriate training and skills development to foster the use in SMEs.

Figure 1: HumanTech interaction of technologies

The availability of a dynamic detailed representation of the current state of the construction with frequent updates is the enabler for intelligent robotic and wearable applications in human-machine coexistence and collaboration. Wearable technologies can provide health-related information of the workers, while visualization devices such as AR glasses can overlay information from the digital twin on the view of the worker. Semantic information of the environment can be used to trigger task-dependent exoskeleton components to assist the worker. Finally robotic devices can use the digital twin information for autonomous task decision and localization/path planning.

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All partners involved in HumanTech envision that advances towards a greener and safer construction industry will be achieved when different technologies are fused together towards an advanced robotic task execution under the lead and supervision of a human operator and worker supported by wearable devices with intelligent transparency and in full control of the robot through unobtrusive, intuitive interfaces that require realistic training and costs, especially for the majority of small companies in the construction sector (see Figure 1).

Before the state-of-the art (section 3) and research requirements (section 4) are further elaborated on, the challenges for the construction industry will be described.

2. Challenges of the construction industry

Long-term megatrends are significantly changing peoples' needs and have, therefore, a big impact on how the construction industry needs to evolve. Besides renovation of the EU building stock for a reduction of the energy consumption and decarbonisation two main megatrends affecting the sector are Urbanisation and Mobility and Infrastructure Investments [1]:

- Urbanisation - By 2025, it is estimated that 81.1 % of the population in Western Europe will live in urban regions (84.1 % by 2040) [2]. The resulting densification requires new housing concepts that can be flexibly adapted to different lifestyles and phases of their inhabitants and are designed to be not only ecologically and economically but also socially sustainable.
- Mobility and infrastructure investments - By 2040, it is estimated that 13.9 trillion € (\$14.8 trillion) will have to be invested in mobility and infrastructure in Europe [3]. The way people want to be mobile is becoming more individual and complex, but at the same time, it should conserve natural resources. The corresponding infrastructure must also be geared to this.

In addition to the megatrends on the demand side, drastic changes in the industry will also shape the construction sector in the coming years. Through prefabrication of modules in factories, advancing industrialisation can contribute to increase the productivity of the construction industry but this must also consider the reality of micro and small construction companies, which represent most of the sector, and which will need significant accompanying and support measures to effectively embrace these transition processes. Digitisation helps to improve the design of construction projects and processes, for example, through the universal application of Building Information Modelling (BIM) via digital lean construction methodology to Integrated Project Delivery (IPD). The trend towards ecologically and socially sustainable solutions in construction will continue to grow due to increasing demand from private clients, investors and developers as well as the efforts of the companies themselves. [1]

While fulfilling the increased demand for infrastructure and housing as well as renovation projects, construction industries need transform towards a greener and safer working environment resulting in the need of rapid and disruptive change. To illustrate this, the situation regarding the demand for concrete and its climate impact is given in

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the info box with concrete and cement production causing 8 % of global GHG emissions [2].

Concrete, as one of the main building materials, has a high demand on resources like water, sand and aggregates which are already scarce in some regions. Hereby, the need for a rapid change towards a resource efficient and climate friendly industry is illustrated explaining the environmental impact of concrete and cement production. Besides, other non-renewable materials such as steel, plastics, gypsum or chalk have a considerable effect as well.

Cement, which is a main component of concrete, is responsible for around 8 % of the global greenhouse gas emissions (GHG emissions) [2]. The global development during the last years shows an almost steady increase of the cement production and with that an increment of the GHG emissions caused by it [3]. This increase could partly be explained by the growing world population. But while the population grew by about 35 % between 1994 and 2018 [4] the cement production tripled within this period.

Therefore, there must be an additional reason for the significant increase of cement production. When looking at the global GDP [5] as an indicator of wealth, it becomes evident that it increases by the same percentage as the cement production volume in the considered period; a connection is likely. This connection could be illustrated and explained with the increase of living space per capita caused by wealth. For example, in Germany it doubled between 1960 to 2010 from 20 m² to 40 m² [6] and is prognosed to increase by additional 15 m² until 2030 [7]. This would correspond to tripling between 1960 and 2030.

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The described development implies an increase in GHG-emissions and a decrease of the availability of resources. Therefore, construction industry needs to adopt the goals of the Green Deal [8] and the Paris Agreement and initiate a rapid change, taking into consideration the reality of the sector and its companies. A rough calculation could be used to estimate the emission goals of the global cement production: Regarding the German saving targets the GHG-emissions need to be reduced to 35 % compared to the level in 1990. Considering the tripling of cement production between 1990 and 2022 as well as the estimation of a constant cement demand until 2030, the GHG-emissions need to be reduced to 12 % per ton of cement which corresponds to a decrease of 88 %. As about 2/3 of the emissions from cement production are caused by chemical processes, a potential reduction through switching to renewable energy sources is not enough. Potentials to optimise cement production therefore lie in the combination of thermal efficiency, the fuel mix, and the clinker content. For a further reduction of the emissions up to zero emissions future technologies like carbon capture use and storage (CCUS) are needed. So, besides the optimisation of the production stage a reduction of the used material amount seems to be a comparatively easy implementable solution.

Other challenges of the construction industry lie in the **stagnating labour productivity** as well as in **inefficient processes** in the different stages of construction. A recent study shows that the labour productivity in the construction industry has decreased over the past 25 years [9]. The lack of efficiency gets present when looking at major projects and

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the fact, that during many of them, the calculated costs are exceeded by more than 30 % [10]. Some reasons for that can be found in the organisation structures, the coordination during design and planning processes, risk management and precautionary measures as well as the (lack of) IT-based methods to minder design and building mistakes [11]. Especially the last-mentioned reason is another indicator of the efficiency of a sector. As the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) of the EU [12], the digitalisation index of Germany [13] and a study of McKinsey regarding U.S. economy [14] shows, the construction industry is far behind other sectors in terms of digitalisation.

Construction workplaces are physically demanding. There are several factors, such as manual material handling (lifting of bricks and weights, etc.), awkward work postures (such as in correct way of bending and twisting), hand-arm and/or full body vibration (for e.g., while using hammer drills), which leads to common ailments such as musculoskeletal disorders, breathing or lung issues, strain in upper limb or neck resulting in sick leaves. This seems to make construction unattractive to apprentices and skilled professionals.

For Europe, labour shortage also becomes an increasing problem. In Germany, companies in the building sector reported a labour shortage of 33.5 %, companies in the infrastructure sector of even 37.9 % [15]. In a survey of the European Labour Authority a shortage of many occupation groups related to construction were reported. In the survey involving all 27 EU member states, Iceland, Norway and Switzerland 19 countries reported a shortage on plumbers, truck drivers, carpenters, concrete placers and finishers, bricklayers, electricians, civil engineering technicians and others were reported [16]. Seven of the involved countries reported a high shortage (i.e., more than 3 % lack of labour in the occupation group) in plumbers, and pipe fitters and welders, six reported a high shortage in brick layers [16]. In Japan over 60% of construction companies reported labour shortage. India on the other hand, is experiencing a labour shortage of around 15-20% [17].

To anticipate the mentioned challenges involving urbanisation and construction demand, climate change and resource scarcity as well as inefficiency and labour shortage, a wide range of answers will have to be found. Based on a technology driven research, HumanTech will contribute to solutions aiming at overcoming these challenges. To identify research needs, the state-of-the-art will be analysed in the next section.

1. State-of-the-art

2.1. Semantic reconstruction and modelling

The ability to construct accurate representations of the built environment can enhance task execution within the construction process for tasks such as fabrication, installation, quality control, progress monitoring, rework, or demolition. Depending on the agent performing the task and the desired outcome, each of them requires a unique semantic interpretation of the built environment. These semantic interpretations would rely on the as-built data informing the as-modelled BIM and vice versa. Within the HumanTech setup the evolution of the as-modelled BIM is handled by the BIMxD formats.

The as-built information in HumanTech will be gathered using the various RGB-D sensors handled either independently or mounted on capture platforms. Using the point cloud, image and other multimodal data gathered by these sensors, task specific semantics such as material, building element type, demolition candidate, etc; or state specific semantics such as built/installed correctly/incorrectly, under-construction, etc can be inferred to enhance the BIM representation.

To accomplish this, in HumanTech, we plan to leverage and extend the state of the art in 3D semantic segmentation [18], [19]. Since construction sites are extremely noisy and cluttered environments, there is a need to develop algorithms that are invariant to various forms of deformations to onsite geometry [20]. As leveraging advances in equivariant representations for point cloud data [21], [22] we plan to develop new algorithms for extracting semantic representations of the as-built environment allowing us to infer both state and task specific semantics. To augment the geometric information inferable from the point cloud data, we also plan to leverage the texture information from image data to enhance the semantic representation of the as-built model. Building on advances in the state of the art in image based semantic segmentation [23], [24] we seek to extend these methods to work on spherical panoramic images within the HumanTech project. We also plan to exploit the state of the art in semantic segmentation to allow us to accelerate the labelling of sensor data [25], [26] collected on different construction sites to build task-specific machine learning models to be used within the context of HumanTech.

2. Wearables

Exoskeletons are divided into categories based on the nature of their assistance. Passive exoskeletons rely on elastic elements (springs, rubber bands) for storing and returning the supporting energy, while active exoskeletons are equipped with electric/pneumatic/hydraulic actuators [27]. Passive exoskeletons are the most widespread in the industry (they are cheaper, simpler, and lighter, and require less maintenance), but they provide low level of assistance and flexibility.

The personalization in passive exoskeletons goes through the manual adjustment of several mechanisms at the beginning of each task. If the task is complex, it may involve different movements for which a single setting might not work, this issue may be quite demanding and could reduce the acceptance of the exoskeleton. The “on-off” adjustment present in [28] consists of a clutch which engages/disengages the mechanical storage element (spring) to allow force development. A third category of exoskeletons, semi-passive, or hybrid exoskeletons can modify its behaviour in an “automatic” way, by pure mechanic solutions. Examples are exoskeletons for lumbar support [29], or through small electromechanics/actuators [30].

To automatically modify its behaviour, the exoskeleton must have knowledge about the human’s planned actions and its environment, using sensors to infer the intention.

One option is Force Sensitive Resistors (FSRs), wireless pressure shoe insoles, encoders, electroencephalogram (EEG) as well as electromyography (sEMG) [31]. For these there is a trend to use well-known AI techniques for interpretation of the signals and learning the models. Linear discriminant analysis (LDA), support vector machines (SVMs) and artificial neural networks are common approaches when dealing with EEG or EMG signals [32]. Few examples of exoskeletons applying deep learning for predicting user’s motion can be found [33].

Another option is using inertial measurement units (IMUs), which typically consist of accelerometers, gyroscopes, and magnetometers. These are particularly useful to determine the wearers kinematics [34]. Within an industry or construction environment, however, the magnetometers which contribute to the global yaw estimate, are likely to be disturbed easily. This is a challenge when the relative orientation of multiple sensors is relevant [35]. Here, model-based tracking provides a good solution which provides a method to maintain intrinsic accuracy if enough motion is present [36]. The usage of biomechanical models, however, comes with another set of problems: the model

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dimensions and how the sensors are placed on different body segments are a priori unknown. This can be solved with anthropometric tables and calibration postures [37], or, with enough motion or under the assumption of kinematic constraints, with self-calibration methods [38].

Another way to find the kinematics and use them to recognize the user's intention, is by wearing a spherical camera, that captures the whole body. On the image, neural networks can detect joint points [39]. Besides capturing the kinematics, it can also be used for localization (maybe in combination with an IMU [40]) and/or object detection which might add information to the intention prediction, especially when objects are related to certain task. If these objects are rigid, their detection can be used for semantic localization [41].

Once the user intention has been recognized, the exoskeleton will try to assist him/her during the task, in several ways depending on other constraints. The null space of a task consists of all the possible solutions which lead to the same target. The selection of a solution from the set will depend on the objectives of other "secondary" tasks. Null-space control is a very well-known technique in robotics that allows e.g. autonomous robot manipulators [42] or unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) [43] for keeping their goal while avoiding the obstacles. Although lots of references can be found for interactive robots and humanoids, there is no literature about its application for exoskeletons.

Gamification based on XR technologies (Virtual reality, augmented reality, etc.) has been widely used in exoskeleton-based rehabilitation to retain and increase the interest of the patients, so they keep performing the exercises of their therapy. There are evidences that such novel way of interfacing improved the motor function of the patients [44]. The approach in occupational exoskeletons has been different, taking the advantage of these elements for the identification of the optimal areas and tasks for application, the fine tuning of the elements of the exoskeleton based on simulation results and the effective and safe training of workers into the correct use of different exoskeletons [45].

XR encompasses a spectrum of technologies that superimpose the virtual world with the real world. These technologies can leverage, to various degrees, visual, auditory, and/or haptic information to provide virtually immersive experiences for users [46]. Visual and/or auditory guided XR is often mediated by some form of wearable smart-glass or lens, which allows users to visualize and subsequently interact with three-dimensional virtual content, often with some degree of auditory flow. Visualization in this

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manner offers a powerful medium for critical information delivery for personnel at the workplace, and indeed XR technologies are currently being used for such purposes in a variety of industrial and employment settings [47, 48]. Practical applications range from virtually guided assistance in accomplishing specific tasks, to facilitation of training, and even to ensure the safety of workers at the workplace [49].

Studies on the efficacy of XR usage for these practices, measured by performance and training ability, reveal a substantial influence in augmenting these practices when utilizing XR [47, 50]. Wearable XR technologies of this style, as mentioned previously, are typically of the smart-lens type, although other options are available, such as handheld modern smartphones or tablets. The latter are a less practical solution for workplace usage, as the former are worn on the head and permit workers to keep their hands available for use. Various types of wearable AR/VR headsets exist and can be selected depending on the goal and desired immersive level of the XR experience [49] e.g., augmented versus virtual reality settings; AR and VR, respectively.

A common feature among these devices is in their low computational capacity e.g., [51], which make high-resolution holographic visualizations of complex or detailed virtual content suboptimal and impractical. A modern and innovative solution to mitigate this limitation is by offloading the computationally heavy processes from the XR device to a computer/server which has high processing capabilities, and subsequently streaming the rendered content to the XR device [51, 52]. Remote rendering and streaming in this fashion offer a modern way of ensuring optimal XR conditions for users, as e.g., shown by visualizations of complex city structural data [51]. Remote rendering and streaming will be employed in the HumanTech project for high quality visualizations of BIM industrial data and for as-needed information delivery. Further, the solutions used in HumanTech will enable streaming of entire XR applications, which permit high quality integrations with the HumanTech digital environment.

2.2. Automation and Human-Robot interaction

Robots are already used in elderly care, space applications, rescue assignments and now slowly but gradually also in construction sites. Behavior and cognitive skills of a robot working in a construction site is especially challenging and requires multidisciplinary collaboration between robotics, cognitive sciences, ergonomics and psychology [58].

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Figure 2: Human-Robot Communication

In human-robot interaction it should be the human that assigns a common goal for both, and the challenge for the robot is to assist the worker by understanding the human's intention and carrying out corresponding supportive tasks.

To assist the human in achieving

a set of goals, the robot must estimate human intentions communicated explicitly or implicitly and act accordingly. The main communication channels are speech, gesture, haptic signals, and physiological signals as illustrated in Figure 2.

Human speech is a natural way of communication and it can inform a partner explicitly with very complex information and structure [53, 54]. Robots use speech recognition to estimate the human intentions and synthesize speech to report back to the human. Self-supervised learning has been shown to improve speech recognition while requiring less annotated data [55].

Another way of communication is by producing visual signals such as gestures and projection of primitive signs [62, 63]. Robots can estimate the human intentions from gestures through gesture recognition. There are many ways to inform another partner about her or his intention by using visual signals. Robots can produce visual signals and inform humans about status or challenges in each task. The visual signals a robot can use are facial expression, arm gestures or projection of signs. Haptic communication is also a way of extracting information by using either force, torque, angles, and orientation to understand a human intention.

Haptic communication can be applied in a situation where a human and a robot are manipulating an object together [64]. Implicit communication of intention such as physiological response is very complex and requires a high level of cognition [65]. Physiological signals can be used to derive an intention based on signals from brain, muscle activity and heart rate.

Ongoing research projects are focusing on a multimodal interface with deep learning capabilities for classification and recognition [66–68]. These approaches combine intelligent computer vision and speech control capabilities. Using a multimodal

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interface, the human can transfer information of a 3D point, lines, and trajectories using hand and finger gestures and voice recognition to assist the human in estimating parameters and interacting with the robot's state machine.

3. Research Requirements

3.1. BIMxD – An extended BIM representation

Common open BIM standards, mainly Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) are focused on the exchange of semantically enriched 3D representations during the planning stage of construction projects, with additional specifications allowing data exchange in the construction, operation, and demolition phase of the item. They are aimed to support different types of use case scenarios, allowing the users to develop specific workflows for data exchange. In the HumanTech project aiming at the application of a wide range of technology in construction, standards for the data exchange towards an extended BIM formulation will provide solutions as follows:

- 1) Semantical and technical interoperability, standardizing the information exchange between the construction project and devices or platforms, and
- 2) Scheduling of tasks for robots on the decision level e.g., initiating a robotic / drone data acquisition mission or a robotic task execution.

The international organisation buildingSMART works on the extension of open standards for BIM data exchanges and promote these actions that operate on a process level and on an operative level:

- 1) Process level: use of IDM (information Delivery Manual) in order to understand who the actors of the process are and which kind of information they have to exchange on a semantic and geometrical level,
- 2) Practical level: use the existing data model (IFC – Industry Foundation Classes [56]) that allows to represent the built construction objects, their geometry, and their attributes. Moreover, the standard can be implemented and adapted using a data dictionary which is a collection of domain-specific terms, classifications, and properties.

The open-source BIM authoring tool will achieve fully productive use in HumanTech workflows to be deployed. Any advances relevant to standards will be integrated into construction practice. On the process level an IDM (information Delivery Manual) of the different HumanTech processes (robotic demolition, etc.) will be developed to define the specific activities and the information requirements. Identifying which kind of information are required from the built environment contained in the BIM models for automation planning and human-robot collaboration [57], [58].

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From the IFC data model objects entities present in the HumanTech workflows will be adopted and used. Possible gaps in the data model will be identified. Subsequently, an IFC extension will be suggested from BIMxD specifications and transferred into standardisation processes [59]. On the geometry level, geometric representation rules (IfcRepresentation resource) will be defined. On the semantic level, standard properties (IfcPropertySingleValues) and property sets (IfcPropertySet) that are required for describing the robotic tasks and human-robot collaboration will be developed.

A HumanTech ontology for each process will be developed involving:

- 1) Implementation of a bSDD data dictionary with the ontology of the human-robot collaboration using the classification from an open repository for classification schemas and information specifications for open BIM data exchange. Later, the application of HT project results will be open to any end-user in the construction industry. [60–62]
- 2) Definition of an IDS (Information Delivery Specification). The IDS will be shared and implemented in machine readable way to meet the requirements of different BIM-based platforms: the focus is then to carry an Information Delivery Manual (IDM) and Templates for open source BIMxD authoring. [63]

3.2. DSDT – Semantic Digital Twin – Scan2BIM approach

For the generation of a semantic digital twin (Scan2BIM), the task can be divided into multiple subtasks beginning with generating semantic labels and detecting geometric primitives from the input raw sensor data such as point cloud scans and images. The semantic labels are then used to reconstruct the 3D model of the captured scene.

The neural network algorithms developed build upon the state-of-the-art (see section 3.1) to generate the required labels from the respective input data. The goal is to benefit from the different sensor modalities to create a holistic understanding of the scanned environment. This step of algorithm development relies heavily on supervised learning through large scale annotated datasets.

These methods will commence with training on current publicly available indoor datasets such as [64] and [65], and possible future datasets. The networks can then be fine-tuned on data captured and manually annotated within the HumanTech project. This data is acquired from 360° ToF (time of flight) and RGB cameras as well as UGV (unmanned ground vehicle) and UAV (unmanned aerial vehicle) generated 3D scans.

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To leverage the benefits of large data, synthetic data generation is done from simulations [66] using the BIM model information of the scanned data. To bridge the gap between the simulated sensors and realistic scans techniques such as Sim2Real and GAN [67, 68] based approaches are used.

Figure 3: Semantic segmentation of point clouds

The predicted semantic labels can be used for the further semantic reconstruction towards a BIM. The first step is filtering the point cloud according to the predicted labels, a step that can be achieved trivially by using the representation of the labels as integer or RGB values. Subsequently, point cloud segments need to be clustered to perform a semantic instance segmentation. For clustering, density based clustering such as DB-SCAN [69] and primitive fitting methods such as RANSAC [70] will be used and improved where necessary. From the instance segmentation, the geometric parameters can be obtained using methods to estimate the minimum bounding box as suggested in [71] and approaches such as region growing or void growing as the inverted approach, recently under evaluation in the HumanTech tasks.

The geometric parameters are used to generate a BIM model using open-source BIM tools such as IfcOpenShell [72] and BlenderBIM, a full integration of the IfcOpenShell in Blender [73]. Open data formats such as Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) [56] and an extended BIM formulation (see section 4.1) will be used to allow for interoperability and accessibility of the data.

The resulting BIM will be validated against accurate ground truth data. A good option is to use data from terrestrial laser scanners that is referenced against a conventional survey in a local or global coordinate system. The accuracy of the resulting BIM can be quantified estimating the cloud-to-BIM distance.

3.3. Integrated wearables with intelligent transparency

Construction is not as structured an environment as the automotive industry is, since the product is not movable but the company that delivers/renovates it is. Continuous adaptations must be carried out by the workers: different geographical and spatial

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considerations, varying order of operations, different posture for accomplishing the tasks, a wide range of objects or tools to be manipulated, different products to handle, etc. It is not the optimal playground for traditional exoskeletons, designed for the assistance in workplaces where there are only little variances. The constantly changing conditions in the operation will require frequent activation and adjustment which can be quite demanding for the user. It is thus likely that the user will reject the technology. HumanTech aims to create more intelligent exoskeletons that will respond to the needs of construction workers and companies, thus improving the acceptance of the technology, facilitate a wider adoption and improving worker's health.

The exoskeleton to be designed and developed in HumanTech will be of a hybrid passive/active approach that will benefit from the advantages of both kind of elements. Regarding passive elements, there are some limitations this research will deal with: low flexibility/capability of adaptation and low level of assistance. HumanTech partners will work on smart electromechanical systems to overcome these weaknesses. The components should be characterized by being just-mechanical or low-power while being less demanding for the user. The proposed elements will identify the user's intention, activating or deactivating key features, providing support for critical actions when needed, but rendering the exoskeleton more transparent and unobtrusive to the user when performing other non-assisted activities. To infer such intention and act accordingly, the exoskeleton controller will combine the information coming from an integrated network of wearables constituted by IMUs, a body-sensor network and on-body camera. Since each of the mentioned components will run their own controller, it would be desirable to share the same microprocessor to reduce the weight of the on-body system. Sharing one processor will be also useful to avoid delays in communication between components, especially in those loops running at very high rates.

The user's action for activation/deactivation can be adjusted to a greater or lesser degree of voluntariness. HumanTech exoskeleton will exploit a null-space concept, widely used in robotics but never applied to exoskeletons, letting the user learn that if the user wants the exoskeleton to act in a particular way, the user should position their body in a specific (but natural) pose within the null space before making the movement. By choosing which joint motion for a specific task, the user can naturally activate or deactivate assistance without needing to explicitly press a button or otherwise change the operating mode.

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As mentioned above, construction environments are dynamic and multivariate by nature. Such sites are structurally intricate, and present with a high complexity in their geometric and semantic components. For workers to navigate and subsequently operate efficiently and safely, XR smart glasses will be used to provide high resolution holographic visualizations of BIMxD model data. Using these virtual visualizations, workers will be able to better, and more appropriately, localize themselves in their environments with respect to updated and relevant geometrical coordinates of the construction site, as well as be provided a platform for pertinent information delivery if needed. HumanTech will make use of the digital twin BIMxD data for this purpose, and combined with XR visualization, will lead to better training environments, which increases the safety, well-being, and performance of workers. These measures will enable workers to be more efficient and accurate in the fulfilling of their tasks and will offer a platform for workers to be better informed about themselves and their environment. Investigation into the former will be done to determine to what extent other HumanTech wearable data (e.g., positional ergonomic data) can be utilized with XR visualizations for relevant information delivery.

In line with the HumanTech intelligent transparency goal, XR devices will be used on-demand. Given that localization data will be provided by the wearable sensors instead of the XR device, a deviation from typical XR processing, users will be able to make use of the smart glasses when required. Remote rendering and subsequent streaming of the XR data mentioned above to the XR device will be used to enable high resolution and quality visualizations, which bypasses current limitations in the computational ability of stand-alone XR devices. Indeed, without offloading, remote rendering, and streaming of this content, such visualizations would not be of suitable level necessary for working in construction sites with the data mentioned above.

3.4. Robotic interfaces and learning from demonstration

Learning from demonstration is the name of the paradigm that brings together all the techniques involved in a human teaching a robot.

Three techniques are commonly used to make the robot acquire capabilities from a human: passive observation, kinesthetic teaching, and teleoperation. In the case of passive observation, the user is not in contact with the robot and the recognition of actions is mostly done by vision and a subsequent embodiment mapping is necessary

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between the movements of the human and those that would be necessary in the robot. Kinesthetic teaching eliminates the need for embodiment mapping as the human guides the robotic arm with his/her hands and the robot executes the task itself guided by the human. The problem comes when the robot shall be guided in hazardous, remote, or sterile environments. In these cases, it is not safe for the human to be in physical contact with the robot and here is where teleoperation shows its potential as it allows the human to perform the demonstrations remotely with the same robot that will then execute the task, avoiding the embodiment problems and keeping the human in a safe environment.

But unlike in kinesthetic teaching where the only requirement for the robot is to be able to be moved freely, teleoperating a robot manipulator requires being able to control the individual joints' position or velocity at a sufficiently high rate because the teleoperation performance will continuously degrade the lower the control rate is. In addition to the rate, the commands must not go through a trajectory interpolation system. This requirement can be slightly relaxed if the interpolation is sufficiently fast and can adapt to a moving target, i.e., no stopping at each individual position.

From the learning perspective, although a single demonstration could be enough to execute the task in exactly the same way as demonstrated, in HumanTech we believe that using several demonstrations will provide us with information about the environment and will allow us to know the areas where the movement of the robot has to be stiffer as the variability between demonstrations will be minimal or where the movement can be laxer as the variability will be greater.

Having learning techniques that can adapt to changes within the demonstrated trajectory and that are not simple reproductions of a single demonstration, is vital in the field of construction, given that the environment in hand will be variable and unstructured.

Therefore, the main objectives of the related tasks during the project are: 1) to create teleoperation interfaces so that an operator who does not have robotics background will be able to demonstrate a task a few times, and 2) to implement algorithms capable of being trained in a short time so that the automation of the process is fast and agile.

3.5. On site Human-Robot interaction

For the research on human-robot collaboration in HumanTech, the main objective is to design and develop a communication channel based on gesture, projection, and speech between the on-site or virtual control environment and the physical robot enabling supervision and real-time communication.

The demonstration of new human-robot interaction abilities is based on a brick delivery pilot case. A brick wall will be built by a human and a robot collaboratively. The robot's role is transportation and handing over, the human worker receives the brick and builds the wall with it.

The human-robot collaboration consists of 2 main components, 1) human-robot communication and 2) environment perception. The human-robot communication component ensures that the robot can understand the command given by the human. At the same time, the robot provides feedback to the human about its upcoming actions. The robot understands its surrounding on the construction site through the environment perception component. This component allows the robot to locate and pick up the bricks.

The human-robot communication component can be divided into multiple subtasks, these subtasks are speech-based interaction, gesture/pose recognition, projection-based interaction, and overall system logic and fusion of different communication technologies.

For speech-based interaction, a voice command recognition library will be developed to enable a robot to decode human speech into commands or tasks. As well as a speech generation library for communicating back with a synthetic speech. Further research and further development of methods for gesture/pose recognition will be initiated. The use of both close-range hand gestures and long-range arm gestures to influence robotic motions will be examined. For projection-based interaction an application will be developed informing a human about the robotic tasks and operations using a projector. A projector can be mounted on AGV and thus shows parts of the planned AGV path, or a projector can be mounted on robot flange to point at objects at the destination.

In the aspect of the environment perception component, two subtasks need to be solved with computer vision technology, namely brick and human localization. A brick localization (6 degree-of-freedom pose estimation of brick) module will be developed to

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find the bricks and determine the pose of each brick, which is essential information for brick grasping. The deep learning algorithm for brick pose will be trained at category-level, meaning that it will be able to estimate the pose of bricks both previously seen and unseen in the training data. After the robot collects enough bricks, it transports them to the human. A human localization task calculates the position and orientation of humans in 3D. Based on this information, the robot estimates the delivery position of bricks.

3.6. Workflow capturing and XR visualization

Based on the semantic digital twin 3D representation it is possible to generate 3D scene graphs as an additional representation [74]. A 3D scene graph captures the relations between semantic entities in a scene making it an efficient, low-memory abstracted representation of a scene, compared to full 3D models. Such a high-level representation makes comparisons and detection of changes in scene graphs much simpler than direct examination of 3D point clouds or large-scale 3D models.

Figure 4 Scene graph generation, update, and

In HumanTech we aim to characterize a workflow and track the progress of construction projects by generating scene graphs at different time intervals and comparing them to detect changes in specific element, e.g., a new wall,

window, etc. This will allow direct and automated documentation of progress between different scans. One method to visualize these changes on-site will be to use the AR/XR wearable glasses and highlight for example the newly added/modified construction elements (see Figure 4).

4. The Impact of HumanTech

4.1. Worker safety and health

Ensuring a safe and healthy working environment is an essential goal for the HumanTech project. We do not only aim at creating working conditions for physical integrity, but above all is the workers' psychological wellbeing our main priority when introducing new technologies to the workplace. Nevertheless, a major aim within HumanTech is to improve the quality of physical strenuous tasks under the physically demanding working conditions in the construction industry. Therefore, we apply a comprehensive approach in HumanTech which includes the following steps. First, we present an overview of relevant regulations to be considered on a technology specific level as well as on a general level. Based on the analyses of large survey data, we are not only able to identify the "typical HumanTech worker" but furthermore typical working conditions and additional characteristics of the construction industry. Based on these findings and knowledge from scientific literature we further define user requirements at an early technology development stage for each of the main HumanTech technologies, potential workers might interact with (interactive robotics/AGVs; exoskeletons; smart glasses).

Secondly, in close collaboration with the HumanTech technology developers the different requirements are considered and discussed at an early development stage. The requirements are amongst others related to aspects of user experience, user acceptance, task design, strain optimisation, simplification, communication, the introduction process and overall enabling a smooth interaction between end-user and system. For these aspects, hardware features as well as behavioural software aspects of the technologies are considered. Furthermore, general privacy and ethics requirements are addressed. In close collaboration with the pilot applications the specific technologies will be evaluated from an end-user perspective allowing a feedback loop to improve the specific technology in question. The end-user evaluation will follow a mixed-method approach using quantitative and qualitative evaluation data.

Highly autonomous systems as well as highly automated tasks hold several risks and challenges for overall wellbeing and additional health-related factors of workers. In HumanTech we follow, as mentioned above, the vision to especially consider essential human-centred principles, like the "human agency and oversight" [75] or the "human-

in-control" [76] principle. The combination of the addressed steps allows us to consider end-user needs and industry specific constraints likewise. As a result, we envision improved working conditions as well as the design and implementation of innovative technologies in a human-centred way.

4.2. Green transition and efficiency

Efficiency can be increased by either boosting productivity through automation, AI and related technologies or by reducing waste of labour and material. The construction industry has always faced enormous problems through incorrect and inaccurate operation, resulting in errors followed by labour-intensive and material-demanding error fixing activities. To overcome errors, increase accuracy and reduce waste of labour and material in construction industry, HumanTech introduces DSDT and BIMxD in combination with wearables to inform the worker better whilst providing a more up-to-date digital model of the site to site to contractors and project managers. Besides, robotic applications will help to reduce labour costs. By these two approaches, HumanTech will have an impact as follows:

- **Reducing error costs.** According to a study based on a survey with 601 participants, the error costs in the turnover of the construction industry rate to 12.8 % in 2020 [77]. The annual turnover of the European construction industry was 1,691.69 billion € in 2020 [78]. Anticipating that the rate of errors is similar in all European countries, Europe faces a waste of labour and material due to errors of about 216 billion € per year. It can be estimated that the application of HumanTech BIMxD, DSDT and Wearable localization and information display could reduce error costs by 1 % or 2.16 billion € per year. This would reduce the waste of labour and material through limitation of errors and result in a reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, and resource savings.
- **CO₂ emissions from errors.** In 2020 3.30 billion tonnes CO₂ emissions were emitted in the European Union [79]. Estimations state that between 5 % and 12 % of these emissions are related to the construction and renovation of buildings [80]. Assuming 10 % of the total emissions are related to the construction and renovation of buildings and dividing the total emissions by the turnover in the construction industry every Euro of turnover relates to 195 g CO₂ emitted. Taking the error costs in construction estimated to 216 billion € per year, all errors would result in 42.1 million tonnes of CO₂ emissions. It becomes obvious, that

construction errors do not only result in error costs, but also in CO₂ emissions that could be easily saved by avoiding such errors.

- **Increase accuracy.** A reduction of error costs would not only help towards a greener construction industry, but an increase of accuracy of work performed on site would help to reduce material used and alleviate labour. Currently, construction from the structure towards finished surfaces (floor, walls, etc) involves multiple layers to evaluate unevenness and inaccuracies. Screed is applied on raw slabs to provide a level and even surface for flooring, plaster is applied to raw brick or concrete walls to provide even surfaces. An increase in accuracy can be facilitated through prefabrication, a common practice in timber and concrete prefabrication of elements or modules. On site, HumanTech provides technology for robotic or XR assisted human tasks to increase accuracy while protecting workers' health and safety.
- **Efficient robotic task automation.** In construction there is a huge number of repetitive tasks. One of these tasks involves carrying material to the specific installation where it is erected or installed. To reduce and alleviate labour within repetitive tasks, HumanTech will deliver robotic solutions to transport material to a specific location autonomously in a collaborative scenario with the human worker fully concentrated on the actual task. This will boost efficiency in construction towards a new level.

As the construction sectors very diverse with different practices on a national and even regional level, quantifying the green impact of HumanTech technologies remains a challenge. All partners will take a joint effort to work on the quantification of advances towards green transition, especially during pilot evaluation.

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